

Improving the Convergence of a Data-Driven Factor Graph Model for UWB-Based Positioning in Challenging Indoor Scenarios

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Abstract—Indoor scenarios can pose challenges for localization. Effects such as multipath and non-line-of-sight propagation between devices can cause errors in positioning systems that utilize radio technologies, even in ultra-wideband (UWB) technology-based systems. Additionally, the geometrical location of the anchor nodes can also impact the positioning error with lateration. In the case of iterative algorithms such as those based on Machine Learning, these effects can affect algorithm convergence. This work presents a solution to enhance the convergence stage of a Data-driven Factor Graph (FG) Model for UWB-based positioning in these scenarios. The FG is represented as a tree, a connected and acyclic graph that ensures convergence of the Gaussian Belief Propagation (BP) algorithm. The new solution utilizes Gaussian Mixture Model fitting to estimate the covariance of distances between the target and anchor nodes. The presented solution is compared with the classical solution that estimates the covariance with a Gaussian fitting. The comparison is conducted using real-life data collected from sensor network nodes compliant with IEEE 802.15.4, featuring a physical layer based on UWB technology. The results show that in challenging scenarios, the presented solution improves the rate of the convergence phase of BP, although at the expense of increased complexity in the FG-based algorithm.

Index Terms—indoor positioning; Ultra-Wide Band; lateration; factor graph; Gaussian belief propagation; convergence

I. INTRODUCTION

Dependable, precise and accurate positioning is vital for numerous location-based services [1] and plays a key role in enhancing communications and mobility management in 5G and upcoming technologies [2]. Other requirements include energy and resource consumption of the positioning system, which are usually related to the algorithm's complexity. Data fusion and machine learning (ML) algorithms can tackle various vulnerabilities of positioning systems, such as multipath or Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) conditions that degrade their performance [3], [4]. This work focuses on algorithms developed using Bayesian inference, implemented via probabilistic graphical models, and employing message-passing algorithms [3]. Consequently, graphical models are considered, such as Bayesian networks [5], which are treated as Factor Graphs (FG) with a Belief Propagation (BP) (or

sum-product) algorithm [6]. In recent years, several FG-based algorithms for positioning and navigation have been introduced [7]–[12].

In the case of FG with BP algorithm for positioning and navigation, multipath or NLOS conditions can affect algorithm convergence [8]–[11]. In references [10], [11], the authors presented a FG algorithm for Ultra-Wide Band (UWB)-based positioning. It is a data-driven FG model for anchor-based positioning. This data-driven FG model deals with propagation conditions and also with the geometrical location of the anchor nodes, overcoming classical algorithms. The FG of [11] is modeled as a tree, a connected graph without cycles that ensures the convergence of the Gaussian BP algorithm [13]. However, multipath or NLOS conditions and geometrical issues can affect its convergence.

This work presents a solution to enhance the convergence phase rate in the Data-driven FG Model of [11], for UWB-based positioning in challenging indoor scenarios. The new solution utilizes Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) fitting to estimate the covariance of distances between the target and anchor nodes. The presented solution is compared to the classical solution that estimates this covariance with a Gaussian fitting. The comparison uses real-life data collected from sensor network nodes compliant with IEEE 802.15.4 [14], featuring a physical layer based on UWB technology. Anchor-based positioning involves two types of nodes: anchor nodes that possess knowledge of their position, and target nodes that lack this information. UWB technology enables ranging and positioning with an error on the order of cm, typically <10cm. The results show the convergence of the algorithm. Moreover, in challenging scenarios the presented solution improves the rate of the convergence phase, but at the cost of increased complexity in the FG-based algorithm.

The remainder of this self-contained paper is organized as follows: the system detailed in [11] is a hybrid structure involving data and modeling, which is adjusted based on distance covariance. In the present work, Section II explains the behavior of the adjustable system and presents the new proposed approach. Section III shows the simulation results

Fig. 1. The Data-driven Factor Graph Model with the main messages μ of the belief propagation algorithm.

using the collected data along with the proposed solution. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROPOSED APPROACHES

The data-driven FG model is a hybrid system that involves data and modeling based on the FG algorithm. It is shown in Fig. 1. Refer to [11] for additional details about the system, messages of the belief propagation and the FG development. The input data of the FG model consists of ranges \underline{d} between target and anchor nodes, as well as anchor nodes positions [11]. It is a linear system that considers Gaussian variables using a Gaussian BP algorithm [11]. In the case of Gaussian BP with linear relationships among variables, the messages μ can be expressed using the mean vector m and the covariance matrix C of the associated Gaussian variable, which simplify the message-passing algorithm in the FG [11]. The covariance estimation of the measurements and variables allows the algorithm to be tunable based on the ranges covariances σ_d^2 of \underline{d} [11].

As shown in Figure 1, the algorithm groups the input distances d . For each group $q = 1 \dots Q$, the algorithm estimates a position \mathbf{x}_q using the Weighted Least Squares (WLS) estimation technique, and also calculates the covariance of this WLS position estimation. It is shown in Figure 1, where each message $\mu_{f_{\Delta d_q} \rightarrow \Delta \mathbf{x}_q}$ is $\mathcal{N} \sim (\Delta \mathbf{x}_q; m_{\Delta \mathbf{x}_q}; C_{\Delta \mathbf{x}_q})$. For WLS, the position and covariance estimation is well known:

$$\mathcal{N} \sim (\Delta \mathbf{x}_q; (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{W} m_{\Delta d_q}, (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H})^{-1}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{W} is the diagonal matrix of weights $w = \sigma_d^{-2}$ and \mathbf{H} is the visibility matrix. The positioning covariance

with the WLS estimation is related to the metric Weighted Geometric Dilution of Precision (WGDOP), which measures the effect on the positioning solution of distance error to the corresponding anchor node and the geometrical situation of the anchor nodes. So, the weight (inverse of the covariance) of each position for each group is related to the WGDOP. Therefore, the algorithm estimates the final position of the target node considering the weighted positions for each group. Thus, the final position \mathbf{x} of the target node is estimated taking into account the propagation and the geometric conditions that influence anchor-based positioning with lateration [11].

A. Solutions for Distance Covariance Estimation

In the solution involving Gaussian fitting, the covariance of the distances σ_d^2 is estimated by fitting a Gaussian distribution to the data during the algorithm initialization, before the iterations of the BP algorithm are performed.

In the solution involving Gaussian Mixture fitting, the covariance of the distances σ_d^2 is estimated as the highest covariance value of a component resulting from fitting a Gaussian Mixture distribution to the data. Each component follows a Gaussian distribution. The number of components of the GMM is c which is estimated by selecting the best fit with the lowest Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) value. This solution implies greater computational complexity. The covariance σ_d^2 is estimated as part of the initialization of the iterative process.

III. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained using the solutions previously discussed. In the figures showing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the position estimation of the target node \mathbf{x} , ‘WLS’ represents the classical iterative algorithm without the FG technique, ‘FG with WLS-Mixture’ refers to the Solution for distance covariance estimation based on Gaussian Mixture fitting with the FG model, while ‘FG with WLS-Not Mixture’ refers to the Solution for distance covariance estimation based on Gaussian distribution fitting with the FG model. The RMSE of the estimated target position, in comparison to its reference position, was calculated as shown in [11].

The results were obtained using data of published datasets that were collected from commercial UWB devices. The ‘‘Datasets of Indoor UWB Measurements for Ranging and Positioning in Good and Challenging Scenarios’’ [15] are available at the Zenodo repository. The datasets were gathered at CTTC’s Indoor Navigation Laboratory. Measurements related to range and positioning were collected using the MDEK1001 system [16], which consists of DWM1001-DEV UWB modules (DW) from Decawave (Qorvo). The nodes are equipped with the DW1000 chip, which complies with the IEEE 802.15.4-2011 [14] standard featuring a UWB physical layer. Anchor nodes were placed on the walls, while the tag node was placed on a tripod. Both the anchor and tag nodes were positioned at specific reference locations, and the coordinates of these reference positions were determined

Fig. 2. Scenarios from [15] that involve node placements on the lab map: the anchor UWB nodes (red triangles) and the target UWB node (black dot).

TABLE I

PROPAGATION AND GEOMETRY CONDITIONS OF EACH ANCHOR NODE

Scenarios	N	Nodes	Conditions	Geometry
A2(Challenging)	4	1d;7 1c;1b	hardNLOS LOS	Medium
A3(Challenging)	3	1c;7;1b	hardNLOS	Medium
A4(Challenging)	4	1d;1b;1a 1c	hardNLOS LOS	Challenging
B(Benign)	4	1c;3;5;6	LOS	Easy
C1(Intermediate)	4	1c;1d;1b;7	softNLOS	Medium
C2(Intermediate)	4	1c;1d;1b;1a	softNLOS	Challenging

using a total station. This static indoor laboratory environment facilitated the setup of scenarios and the alteration of key conditions that influence anchor-based positioning performance, such as varying propagation and geometric conditions. Thus, the UWB DW nodes were mounted in the laboratory at different positions with varying geometrical situations, and propagation conditions (e.g., multipath and NLOS conditions), that affected the positioning error. LOS conditions were taken into account when there were no obstacles between the anchor and tag nodes. Conditions such as *softNLOS* and *hardNLOS* were created with moving obstacles (such as cardboard and metal obstacles, respectively) placed between the anchor node and the tag node in a controlled manner. In the *softNLOS* condition, the range error's standard deviation increased, potentially including a small bias. The *hardNLOS* condition resulted in a higher bias in the range error and a increased standard deviation of the range error.

The results presented were obtained with input data from the following scenarios of the dataset [15]: benign scenario (B), intermediate (C1, C2) and challenging scenarios (A1, A2, A3, A4). The scenarios are shown in Fig. 2. Table I shows the propagation conditions and conditions of the geometrical location of the nodes. Table II shows σ_d with GMM fitting and with the Gaussian one.

In the RMSE results for Scenarios B (see Fig. 3), A1,

TABLE II
TABLE OF SCENARIOS: σ_{d_i} FOR GAUSSIAN AND GMM FITTING.

Sc.	Nodes	$\sigma_d(\text{cm})$ -Gauss.	$\sigma_d(\text{cm})$ -GMM
A2	1c;1d;1b;7	(2.48;4.72;2.21;4.12)	(20.08;246.15;27.37;90.01)
A3	1c;7;1b	(2.55;2.24;6.22)	(50.42;6.22;419.06)
A4	1c;1d;1b;1a	(1.83;2.05;2.15;2.73)	(11.09;17.89;21.66;24.70)
B	1c;3;5;6	(2.18;3.04;2.83;2.09)	(3.9;23.7;24.9;10.04)
C1	1c;1d;1b;7	(2.35;2.84;2.37;3.29)	(6.74;4.10;23.92;8.14)
C2	1c;1d;1b;1a	(1.96;2.94;2.45;2.01)	(15.03;75.3;11.9;6.68)

Fig. 3. Scenario B (RMSE [m] vs. iterations number).

C1 the algorithm converges quickly. The rate (number of iterations until convergence) with GMM is similar to the results with Gaussian fitting. However, the RMSE results for challenging Scenarios A2, A3, A4, and intermediate C2 show the algorithm's convergence rate is higher for the solution based on Gaussian fitting. Furthermore, the results show that the GMM fitting-based solution decreases the rate of convergence for challenging or intermediate scenarios where the algorithm takes longer to converge (see Fig. 4, 5, 6 and 7). The algorithm can be tuned so that the weight (inverse of σ_d^2) of the measurements is reduced, resulting in a larger weight for the model.

For Scenario A2 and Scenario A3, the component number of the GMM fitting selected for each distance data is $c = 2$. For Scenario A4, the component number is $c = 1$ for anchor nodes WALL1c, WALL1d, WALL1b, and $c = 2$ for node WALL1a. And for Scenario C2, the component number is $c = 1$ for anchor node WALL1c, $c = 3$ for WALL1d, $c = 1$ for 1b and $c = 2$ for node WALL1a.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a solution to enhance the convergence stage of a Data-driven Factor Graph Model for UWB-based positioning in challenging indoor scenarios. Multipath and non-line-of-sight conditions between devices and the geometrical location of anchor nodes can impact positioning error when using iteration. Although the FG is structured as a tree (a connected graph without cycles) to ensure convergence of the Gaussian Belief Propagation algorithm, these effects can affect the convergence of the algorithm. The system is a hybrid structure that involves data and modeling, which can be adjusted according to the covariance of distances. The new solution utilizes Gaussian Mixture Model fitting to data to estimate the covariance of distances between the target

Fig. 4. Scenario A2 (RMSE [m] vs. iterations number).

Fig. 5. Scenario A3 (RMSE [m] vs. iterations number).

Fig. 6. Scenario A4 (RMSE [m] vs. iterations number).

Fig. 7. Scenario C2 (RMSE [m] vs. iterations number).

and anchor nodes. This solution is compared to a classical approach, which estimates the covariance with a Gaussian fitting to data. The comparison is performed with collected data from IEEE 802.15.4-compliant sensor network nodes with a physical layer based on UWB technology. Results show that in challenging indoor scenarios, the proposed solution improves the convergence rate of the Belief Propagation algorithm, although at the expense of increased complexity in the FG-based algorithm. In future work, other ranging techniques and positioning with movement will be studied for the FG-based model.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by Grant PID2021-128373OB-I00 (6G-AINA) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, by “ERDF A way of making Europe” and by AGAUR, Generalitat de Catalunya, through the Consolidated Research Group RSE, “Geomatics” (Ref: 2021-SGR-00536) and “Communication Systems Group” (Ref: 2021 SGR 00772).

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